

Conference Abstract

Adaptive management and long-term valuation of forest ecosystem services in Piatra Craiului National Park (LTER Bucegi-Piatra Craiului site): Balancing monetary and non-monetary approaches

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Abstract

The valuation of ecosystem services has become increasingly relevant due to the intricate relationship between humans and ecosystems. In the Piatra Craiului National Park (**LTER Bucegi-Piatra Craiului site**), rapid environmental changes and growing anthropogenic pressures on forest resources necessitate a robust understanding of ecosystem services' value. This study investigates two key aspects:

1. the monetary and non-monetary valuation of forest ecosystem services and
2. the interconnections between these valuations and biophysical variables.

Primary statistical analyses were conducted using the R PASTECS package, revealing notable variability in monetary (141%) and non-monetary (62%) values across management units. Data sources included Forest Management Plans and geospatial analyses derived from photograph datasets. Monetary values ranged from €34 to over

€570,000 per management unit, while non-monetary kernel scores ranged from 1 to 5. Correlations were identified between monetary values and carbon stock, stand volume, and other biophysical metrics, highlighting stronger relationships compared to those involving non-monetary metrics, such as altitude and flora type. A social-media-based approach provided additional insights into the cultural dimensions of ecosystem services, engaging stakeholders and fostering broader public awareness. This integrated methodology underscores the need to balance economic and ecological perspectives in natural resource management. The findings contribute to adaptive management strategies by aligning long-term ecological research with actionable policy recommendations, ultimately promoting sustainable resource use and conservation efforts in the Southern Carpathians.

Keywords

ecosystem service valuation, adaptive management, long-term ecological research, conservation policy, stakeholder engagement

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.